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Abstract

In Nigeria, the ENDSARS protests of 2020 emerged as a national movement against police brutality, especially targeting the Special Anti-Robbery Squad (SARS). This study explores the issues surrounding the protests, the reactions of government and civil society organisations, and their implications for governance in Nigeria. The study is grounded in the Relative Deprivation Theory, which explains protests as responses to perceived gaps between societal reality and expectations. A qualitative methodology was adopted, using secondary sources such as newspapers, journals, media reports, and government documents, analysed through content analysis. Key findings reveal that the protests were rooted in long-standing grievances, which escalated viral incidents of extrajudicial killings, governance issues, human rights issues, and socio-economic grievances. Government responses ranged from repression to partial reforms, while civil society supported for the protesters. Positively, the protests heightened awareness and triggered police reforms, and negatively, they led to economic disruptions, violence, and deepened distrust in governance. The study recommends

full implementation of judicial panel reports, structural police reforms, and enhanced civic engagement to address systemic issues. Strengthening institutional accountability remains essential to restoring public trust and preventing future unrest.

Keywords: *ENDSARS, SARS, Police Brutality, Governance and Human Rights.*

Introduction

The Special Anti-Robbery Squad (SARS) was created in 1992 as a unit of the Criminal Investigation Department of the Nigeria Police Force. The SARS was designed to tackle the serious issue of armed robbery in Lagos, the former capital of Nigeria. SARS achieved significant success in its early years between 1992 and 2002, which led to its operations expanding to other states and its obligation broadening to include the arrest, investigation, and prosecution of suspected armed robbers, hired assassins, kidnappers, murderers, and other violent criminals (Amnesty International, 2020a, b; Ojedokun et al., 2021). However, over the years, some SARS officers engaged in activities beyond their legal responsibilities, leading to calls for its disbandment (Ojedokun et al., 2021).

In recent years, public protests against the Nigerian Police Force were rare, particularly before November 2017. Thus, the ENDSARS protest was unprecedented. The ENDSARS protests were a response to long-standing grievances about the unprofessional conduct of some police officers in Nigeria, especially those in the SARS unit. In 2016, Segun Awosanya (human rights activist) launched the ENDSARS campaign on Twitter, prompting the Nigerian Police Force to announce reforms that were not fully implemented (Mansur, 2017). In 2017, civil society organisations, youths, and celebrities held peaceful protests to raise awareness about SARS brutality and extortion, as well as demanded the unit's disbandment. The ENDSARS gained significant attention on social media, particularly Twitter, with the hashtag ENDSARS (#ENDSARS). This hashtag quickly amassed over 100,000 tweets within a few days, as Nigerians shared their horrible experiences with

SARS operatives (Sahara Reporters, 2017). However, under both online and offline pressure, the government directed the Nigerian Police to reform SARS in August 2018 (Nigeria Police Force's Press Release, 2018). Despite the reformation, some police officers, particularly in SARS, continued to be accused by some Nigerians of acting in ways that violate human rights and abuse power.

In 2020, another ENDSARS protest emerged, eventually leading to civil unrest and mass riots across towns and cities in Nigeria. This protest was fueled by a viral video on social media that showed SARS officials on 3rd October 2020, killing a man in Ughelli, Delta State (Okon, 2020) and the report of the killing of Daniel Chibuikwe, a 20-year-old musician from Rivers, in the Elenwo area of Port-Harcourt (Akinkuotu, 2020). As a result, many Nigerian youths began nationwide demonstrations and protests on Thursday, 8th October 2020. Nigeria's major cities, including Lagos, Abuja, and Ibadan, were the first hit. In Ogbomoso, Oyo State, the protests turned violent on 10th October, 2020, with reports that police killed a young man named Jimoh Isiaka and injured seven protesters. However, the Nigerian Police denied the allegation (Odesola, 2020). Due to increased pressure from protesters, the Nigerian Police announced the dissolution of the SARS unit on Sunday, 11th October 2020. However, the protesting youths did not take the announcement seriously because previous announcements had been poorly enforced. Therefore, the protests continued.

Shortly after SARS' disbandment, the Nigeria Police on Tuesday, 13th October, 2020, created a new unit, the Special Weapons and Tactics Team (SWAT), to discharge the responsibilities of the recently disbanded SARS (So-oriari, 2023). However, the protesters saw this as a mere change of name with the same personnel. This decision angered the protesting youths more (Amnesty International, 2020a). The protesters vowed to continue and intensify their protests. On 20th October 2020, it was considered an unforgettable day in Nigeria's history. On the day known as the 'Lekki Massacre', the Lagos State Government declared a curfew effective from 4 pm WAT, which was later extended to 9 pm WAT. Before the curfew took effect, Nigerian

soldiers arrived, and at the end of the day, they shot at protesters; many were alleged to have sustained bullet wounds, and some died (Amnesty International, 2020b). There have been controversies surrounding the number of people shot and killed in the incident. After the incident of Lekki Tollgate, the ENDSARS protests decreased drastically in physical protests; in the alternative, the protesters continued to amplify their grievances on social media and further pressed their demands on police brutality.

Against this background, this study explores the ENDSARS protest of 2020 in Nigeria, focusing on the issues, the reactions of government authorities, and their implications.

Mass Protest in Nigeria: Roots, Implications and Government Reactions

In the world, particularly in Nigeria, mass protests have historically served as a mechanism for expressing collective grievances in response to governance failures and state repression (Omede & Oladimeji, 2025; Saaida & Alhouseini, 2023; Chaudhari & Pawar, 2021). The ENDSARS protest of 2020 signifies the growing discontent among Nigerian youth towards police brutality and governmental inefficiencies (Iwuoha & Aniche, 2022; Asogwa et al., 2021). Studies (Omede & Oladimeji, 2025; Ecoma, 2023; Usman & Oghuvbu, 2021) revealed the root causes of mass protests in Nigeria and linked them to systemic governance deficits, high unemployment rates, and persistent human rights violations vis-à-vis police brutality. The Nigerian state's tendencies and repressive policing strategies have further exacerbated tensions between the government and its citizens (Irene, 2023). The lack of trust in state institutions, particularly law enforcement, has fueled continuous agitation and civil unrest (Usman & Oghuvbu, 2021). Other studies found that these protests form part of a broader international pattern of youth activism, whereas others emphasise the unique Nigerian socio-political context, where economic insecurity and political exclusion remain prevailing forces behind protests (Dajo & Akor, 2021). In contrast, elsewhere in Africa, especially in Sudan and

Tunisia, protests are linked to similar youth disenchantment and call for structural change (Irene, 2023).

The Nigerian state's response to mass protests drew diverse opinions. Some studies established that the state has failed to engage in serious conversation with mass protesters and instead used violent repression and media censorship (Odili & Egobueze, 2021; Iwuoha & Aniche, 2022). This aligns with authoritarian theories of governance, which postulate that African post-colonial governments prioritise regime stability over democratic engagement (Ecoma, 2023). Nonetheless, some research recognises the government's efforts towards immediate reform, which include the disband SARS and the establishment of judicial panels to probe police abuse (Asogwa et al., 2021). Despite this, doubts remain about the enforcement and effectiveness of such reforms, as reports indicate that police violence continues even though reforms are publicly announced (Nwosu et al., 2022). Besides, studies also questioned the strategic effectiveness of protest in itself; their decentralised leadership, in most cases, enabled mass mobilisation but weakened negotiations with the government, since they lacked a specific post-protest focus (Dajo & Akor, 2021). There are concerns about the sustainability of long-term youth movements in Nigeria and their ability to achieve systemic change in governance.

Apart from their social and political impact, the economic effects of mass protests in Nigeria have also attracted scholarly attention. Ochi and Mark (2021) revealed that the mass protests had significant economic dislocations, including business shutdowns, destruction of public infrastructure, and investor uncertainty. While protests are a means of advocating social justice, they carry economic costs, particularly in developing nations like Nigeria, where political instability hinders foreign investment (Irene, 2023). Nevertheless, the short-term economic distortions caused by protests outweigh the likelihood of long-term benefits from institutional reforms and improved governance (Ecoma, 2023). Furthermore, the role of social media in sustaining and shaping mass protests in Nigeria cannot be overlooked. Social media platforms facilitated rapid mobilisation and

attracted international attention to the movement (Usman & Oghuvbu, 2021). However, concerns have been raised about the spread of misinformation and the potential for digital activism to be manipulated by political actors for personal gains (Iwuoha & Aniche, 2022). These competing narratives underscore the complexity of mass protests in Nigeria, revealing the multifaceted dimensions of political resistance, economic consequences, and digital mobilisation.

Against the above studies, there are a few studies on the ENDSARS protest in 2020, despite its significance in the Nigerian socio-political environment and security apparatus. The existing studies focus solely on issues, reasons, or negative implications; their findings are inconsistent due to the omission or misrepresentation of information. Also, studies have not focused on the government's and Civil Society Organisations' reactions and actions during the ENDSARS protest. Thus, this study seeks to address a significant gap in the literature. This study explores the ENDSARS protest of 2020 in Nigeria, focusing on the issues, the government's responses, and its implications.

Theoretical Framework

Samuel Stouffer developed the Relative Deprivation Theory, which Ted Gurr expanded (Gurr, 2015; Pettigrew, 2015). Theory explains social movements as responses to perceived disparities between expectations and reality. It suggests that when people or groups feel deprived relative to others, frustration grows, which leads to collective action (Gurr, 2015). People protest when they perceive a significant gap between their expectations of social justice and their actual socio-political conditions. This emphasises that deprivation is not absolute but relative; protests arise when people believe they are unfairly disadvantaged compared to others in similar contexts (Gurr, 2015; Pettigrew, 2015). This theory has limitations. A key limitation is its tendency to overlook structural and institutional factors that may contribute to unrest beyond perceived deprivation (Smith et al., 2019). Despite this limitation, the theory remains valuable in explaining mass protests by linking "people's frustrations to social discontent, thereby revealing the psychological motivation behind collective protests (Gurr, 2015).

In this study, the Relative Deprivation Theory is applied to the ENDSARS protests, where Nigerian youths perceived a growing gap between their expectations of security, justice, and governance and the reality of police brutality and state repression. The SARS symbolised institutional failure that fostered feelings of injustice and marginalisation. The frustration escalated into nationwide protests as the government failed to address grievances. The violent crackdown on protesters further reinforced feelings of deprivation, which intensified demands for accountability and systemic reform.

Methodology

The study adopted a qualitative methodology. The qualitative methodologies utilised are a historical study and an exploratory study to assess the ENDSARS protest of 2020 in Nigeria, focusing on uncovering the issues, the reactions of government authorities, and the protest's implications. The study relies on secondary data sources, including newspapers, journals, online publications, government reports, Amnesty International reports, and books (both published and unpublished). The data was collected and analysed using content analysis to achieve the objectives of this study.

Rationale for ENDSARS Protests

In Nigeria, the ENDSARS protests that erupted in October 2020 marked a significant turning point in the country's socio-political environment. For years, Nigerians had reported police abuses, but the government's failure to address them adequately resulted in mounting public anger. The crisis intensified in 2020 when videos of brutality by SARS officers went viral within and beyond Nigeria, organising a massive protest movement. The protests were not only a reaction to the immediate issue of police brutality but also a venting of the resentments of a generation that had long been cowed by the institutions that were tasked with protecting them.

The centrepiece of the protests was the demand for justice and accountability for victims of police brutality, a demand mostly disregarded for years (Amnesty International, 2020a). The Nigerian

police, particularly SARS officers, acted with an impunity that created a vacuum of public distrust in the justice system and police. Many accounts and witnesses attested that SARS officers were often involved in criminal activity themselves, misusing their powers to extort, harass innocent citizens, and employ violent means with impunity. Their victims rarely saw justice, for the systems to bring police officers to account were ineffective or non-existent. This lack of accountability was not just a failure of the police force but also of the governance structure that allowed such abuses to continue unchecked. Therefore, the ENDSARS protests were a call for systemic change, a demand that those in power be held responsible for their actions and that justice be served to the victims of police violence (Amnesty International, 2020a; Ecoma, 2023).

Another issue that led to the ENDSARS protests was socio-economic inequality, particularly affecting Nigeria's youth, who were at the forefront of the protests (Ecoma, 2023). Nigeria has a predominantly young population, but this demographic has long faced significant challenges, including limited access to quality education, high unemployment rates, and a lack of economic opportunities. These issues have been compounded by systemic corruption, economic mismanagement, and poor governance, which have undermined Nigeria's development and left many young people feeling marginalised. The ENDSARS protests provided an outlet for these frustrations, as the protest expanded its demands to include better governance, job creation, and economic reforms. To most young Nigerians, the protests were more than just stopping police brutality. There was a demand for a better future in which they could thrive and realise their full potential. The socio-economic undertones of the protests put into perspective the need for an overhaul reform that went beyond policing and implicated the roots of the youth's grievances (Ecoma, 2023).

The ENDSARS protests raised issues of the rights to freedom of assembly and expression, which came under threat as the government sought to suppress them. The Nigerian Constitution guarantees these

rights, but the government's response to the nationwide protests revealed the fragility of these protections (Amnesty International, 2020a, b). In addition to the use of force, the government employed other means to curb opposition, including the banning of Twitter (X) from 2021 to 2022, harassment of the activists, and freezing the bank accounts of protesters (Ajetunmobi, 2023; Amnesty International, 2020a). All these raised serious concerns about the state of democracy in Nigeria and the extent to which citizens enjoyed rights without fear of persecution. Consequently, the protests became a theatre of defending democratic values and civil liberties in Nigeria. The resilience of the protest in the face of repression attests to the determination of the Nigerian people to ensure their rights and hold their government responsible.

SARS' violation of the right to life was another issue for the ENDSARS protest, which manifested in extrajudicial killings, protester shootings, and other random, unprovoked killings (Ecoma, 2023). In Nigeria, extrajudicial executions are a routine characteristic of policing (Uwazuruike, 2020). Human Rights Watch estimated that the Nigerian police killed over ten thousand (10,000) people between 2000 and 2007 (Human Rights Watch, 2007). For instance, the head of the Enugu State division of SARS allegedly admitted to ordering extrajudicial executions of those he deemed guilty. These killings do not always occur secretly (Uwazuruike, 2020). In August 2019, videos surfaced and went viral, showing how Nigerian police officers executed arrested suspects in Lagos. The suspects, allegedly part of a criminal gang, were summarily executed, and the incident was recorded and went viral. In response, the Nigerian police ordered the involved officers to be arrested (Folarin, 2019). Additionally, the ENDSARS protests of 2020 were fuelled by the viral video that showed how SARS officials killed a man in Ughelli, Delta State, on 3rd October, 2020 (Okon, 2020) and the killing of Daniel Chibuike, a 20-year-old musician in Port-Harcourt (Akinkuotu, 2020), sparking nationwide protests.

Furthermore, the illegal torture of detainees and suspects is another issue raised by protesters. SARS officers routinely subjected individuals

to severe torture to extract “confessions.” This practice was so ingrained that many police stations had officers specifically to oversee torture, designated rooms for this purpose, and even slang for various torture methods (Uwazuruike, 2020). Amnesty International had reported numerous cases of torture, primarily involving detainees in SARS custody. The category of brutality included sexual violence, with detainees and suspects being kicked, beaten with electrical wires, gun butts, machetes, fists, boots, and other instruments, and sometimes bound and suspended in painful positions (Onwunyerimadu, 2022; Uwazuruike, 2020). Additionally, some detainees reported being assaulted and shot in the limbs while in custody, forced to endure painful calisthenics, or suffering multiple fractures. Sex workers particularly reported being rounded up and raped by police officers, with one officer referring to sexual violence as a “fringe benefit” of certain patrols (Uwazuruike, 2020).

Government and Civil Society Organisations’ Reactions to ENDSARS Protests

The ENDSARS protests sparked a range of reactions and counter-reactions from government and civil society organisations (CSOs). Many CSOs, such as ENDSARS Response, Socio-Economic Rights and Accountability Project (SERAP) Nigeria, Feminist Coalition, Mentally Aware NG, ENDSARS Legal Aid, Domino’s Pizza & Coldstone Creamery, The Food Coven, Flutterwave, and others played a crucial role in amplifying the voices of the protesters and advocating for their rights (Lewis, 2020). These organisations provided legal, medical, and humanitarian support to detained or wounded protesters. They also mobilised resources and coordinated solidarity campaigns to galvanise awareness of the underlying issues of the protests, including police brutality, corruption, and impunity. Through grassroots organising and assertive advocacy, CSOs kept pressure and demanded domestic and international reform.

The government responded to the protest with force, for instance, imposing curfews and dispatching security agents to face peaceful protesters rather than hearing their complaints. The Lagos State

Government, for instance, invited the Nigerian Army, which employed brutal methods by shooting live ammunition at protesters, resulting in multiple protesters' injuries at Lekki Tollgate (Amnesty International, 2020a). On the other hand, a coalition of CSOs condemned the military's response to suppress the peaceful ENDSARS protests "at all costs" (Eboigbe, 2020), and the international community condemned the violent crackdown on peaceful protesters by the Nigerian government and its army (Nwafor, 2021).

Furthermore, on the tenth day of the protests, amid significant collateral damage across the nation and with the use of force proving ineffective, the Nigerian government sought a truce with the protesters. They urged the protesters to withdraw, give peace a chance, and allow the government to consider their demands. However, the government's response was seen as too late, as the protests had already caused significant social and economic disruptions nationwide (Ecoma, 2023). Regardless of that, the protesters agreed and issued a five-point demand in addition to their initial call for the disbandment of SARS. The demands were: justice for all deceased victims of police brutality and appropriate compensation for their families; psychological evaluation and retraining (to be confirmed by an independent body) of all disbanded SARS officers before redeployment, in line with the new Police Act; the immediate release of all arrested protesters; the establishment of an independent body to oversee the investigation and prosecution of all reports of police misconduct within 10 days; and an increase in police salaries to ensure they are adequately compensated for protecting the lives and property of citizens (George, 2020).

Amidst the protests, several meetings were held between federal government representatives, state governments, and other stakeholders. From the meetings, the federal government accepted the protesters' demands. In an immediate reaction, the SARS unit was dissolved and replaced with a newly established SWAT Unit. Nevertheless, the protesters rejected the creation of SWAT, seeing it as merely a rebranding of SARS. State governments established judicial panels to investigate human rights abuses by SARS and compensate victims. This

was done by state governments across the federation (Ochojila, 2024). Numerous arrested protesters were freed, and the Nigerian police disclosed intentions to conduct psychological assessments of former SARS officers alongside other proposed reforms (Ewodage, 2020). Following the government's response, the protesters subsequently presented the federal government with an additional seven-point demand (7 for 7) to address broader governance and societal issues. The demands included institutional reforms (security), reduction in the cost of governance, constitutional reforms, education reforms, health reforms, youth development reforms, and public office reforms (Sulaimon, 2020).

To mitigate the effects of protests and accompanying hooliganism, some state governments rolled out various incentives for youth. For instance, in Cross River State, the government directed the employment of 20,000 youths in the state and local civil service. Additionally, Cross Riverine students at CRUTECH were asked to suspend the payment of school fees to support the ENDSARS protests (So-oriori, 2023). Similarly, other state governments introduced various incentives to alleviate the impact of the protests and the country's broader hardship. To curb violence, the Lagos State government announced the prosecution of about 20 police officers for human rights violations (Adediran, 2020).

Despite the government's response to the protesters' demands through police reforms and other actions, the protests grew in intensity, scope, and demands. This is attributed to a significant trust deficit between the government and protesters.

Implications of ENDSARS Protests on Governance in Nigeria

The ENDSARS protests had significant implications (gains and costs). Firstly, one of the significant gains of the ENDSARS protests was the arrest and prosecution of police officials accused of misconduct. The intense pressure from the mass protests led to some ex-SARS officials being held accountable for their actions. On 20th October, 2020, a Presidential Investigative Panel on SARS, assigned to examine allegations of human rights abuses within the unit, advised the removal

of 35 officers, the initiation of legal proceedings against 33 personnel, and the rank reduction of 23 others (Ikhilae, 2020). In response to the protests, several state governors also initiated judicial panels of inquiry to scrutinise incidents of police misconduct and extrajudicial activities linked to the disbanded unit within their jurisdictions (Vanguard, 2020a). However, as of February 2025, most of the established panels' reports had not been implemented, especially those of the Lagos State Judicial Panel, and many had not completed their responsibilities. Nigeria's National Human Rights Commission stated that it had recorded 150 allegations of human rights abuses perpetrated by SARS and the police (Onochie, 2020).

Secondly, a significant outcome of the ENDSARS protests was the initiation of reforms to the Nigerian Police Force and its personnel's working conditions. In response to protesters' demands for improved police welfare, the Nigerian government directed the National Salaries, Income, and Wages Commission on 22nd October, 2020, to develop a revised salary structure for the Nigeria Police Force (Oyero, 2020). Furthermore, as part of broader police reform efforts, the Inspector General of Police issued an order on 4th November 2020 to remove officers assigned to select politicians, organizations, and VIPs (Ayitogo, 2020). Before the ENDSARS protests, deploying police escorts to high-profile individuals was frequently identified as a key factor contributing to the shortage of officers available for public security duties (Network on Police Reform in Nigeria, 2010).

Thirdly, the ENDSARS protests amplified both national and global attention to the widespread issue of police misconduct and the excessive use of force in Nigeria. While police abuse had been acknowledged for years, victims and eyewitnesses of brutality had never before possessed such a significant platform to publicly share their experiences and demand justice (Akinlabi, 2017). The public campaign not only increased awareness about citizens' rights to seek redress against police brutality but also underpinned the power of social media in holding personnel accountable. As a result, police officers are now more

cautious in their interactions with the public, knowing that any misconduct could be recorded and publicly posted on social media.

On the other hand, the ENDSARS protests had significant repercussions for Nigeria's policing and law enforcement. At their inception, the protests began peacefully, but they eventually turned violent, which led to a breakdown of law and order in over 23 states (Vanguard, 2020c). Some individuals exploited the situation to loot government and private property, burgle stores, warehouses, and residences, vandalise public properties, commit arson, and forcibly release inmates from custodial facilities (The Punch, 2020). The situation deteriorated to the point where many governors had to impose curfews. This aligns with Reynolds-Stenson's (2017) assertion that protests against police brutality led to widespread confrontations, property damage, and violence. Moreover, the ENDSARS protests exposed the vulnerabilities in Nigeria's cybersecurity infrastructure, as numerous government and corporate websites were hacked by a cyber-anonymous group in solidarity with the protesters (The Nation, 2020a).

Similarly, the ENDSARS protests led to the deaths of police officers and the destruction of police facilities across Nigeria (The Punch, 2020). The protests' rapid escalation resulted in violent encounters between protesters and law enforcement, during which police officers shot and killed some protesters. In retaliation, some protesters targeted police officers and stations. The Nigerian Police reported that 22 police officers were killed and over 205 police stations and formations were damaged during the protests (Vanguard, 2020b).

The ENDSARS protests had negative implications for policing and law enforcement, as they further deteriorated the police-community relations in Nigeria. Historically, this relationship has been marked by mutual distrust and detachment. The public generally views police officers as unprofessional, while police officers see the public as hostile. The ENDSARS protests and the associated violence against law enforcement occurred. In the weeks following the protests, many police officers in several states refrained from performing their duties (The Nation, 2020b). This absence of law enforcement led to a surge in

crimes such as armed robbery, mob killings, rape, looting, and extortion in some cities (Iyatse & Eniola, 2020).

Conclusion

The ENDSARS protests of 2020 were a landmark movement in Nigeria's socio-political environment that revealed deep-seated issues of police brutality, governance inefficiencies, and youth disenchantment. The protests were a reaction to the unchecked excesses of the SARS, and quickly evolved into a demand for systemic reforms, accountability, and respect for human rights. Despite the government's dissolution of SARS, the perceived lack of sincerity in implementing reforms continued to fuel distrust between citizens and the authorities. The violent dispersal of protesters, especially at the Lekki Tollgate, further exposed the fragility of democratic governance and civil liberties in Nigeria. Although the protests opened a global debate about police brutality and the strength of online activism, they also evidenced the risks of state repression and the advantages and disadvantages of youth-led movements without formal leadership. The aftermath of the protests, including the establishment of judicial panels of inquiry and the proposed police reforms, suggests an ongoing struggle between the demand for change and its resistance. Ultimately, the ENDSARS movement underscored the need for holistic governance reforms that extend beyond policing to address economic instability, youth unemployment, and structural inequalities in Nigeria.

Recommendations

Coordinated efforts are necessary and should be undertaken by the principal stakeholders (the Nigerian government, the Nigerian Police, Nigerians, and CSOs) to prevent and manage future occurrences of mass demonstrations and sustain police reforms. To begin with, the Nigerian government should make deliberate efforts towards rebuilding trust among the public by implementing the judicial panels' recommendations against police brutality in their entirety to provide justice to the victims and instituting genuine police reforms that go beyond cosmetic restructuring. Second, the Nigerian Police Force should accord top priority to internal accountability structures, retrain

officers to respect human rights, and establish independent oversight bodies to transparently investigate cases of police malfeasance. Also, the welfare and working environment of the police officers should be improved to reduce corruption and illegitimate avenues. Third, Nigerians, particularly the youth, should continue to be positively engaged in the exercise of civic rights, advocacy, and the demand for good governance through lawful avenues, so that their complaints are channelled constructively to prevent hijacking by hooligans and opposing groups. Lastly, Civil Society Organisations (CSOs) should continue to act as watchdogs by providing legal aid to victims, placing the government on its guard, and facilitating dialogue between citizens and the authorities. Also, CSOs need to invest in civic education to empower Nigerians to know their rights and their role in governance. It is only through such collective efforts that Nigeria can move towards a more equal, accountable, and democratic state.

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